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Factors Affecting the Level of Stress and Burnout among the Teachers in the New Normal

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Abstract

The goal of the study was to ascertain how workplace stress in the teaching professional relates to teachers' ability to perform as teachers. The descriptive-correlation survey method, was used in this study. Results indicated that respondents had high levels of job stress; yet, teachers' attitudes and performance levels were also highly satisfying. There was no significant association between a respondents profile and their workplace stress in the teaching profession. The workplace stress and attitudes towards the organization were significantly correlated, as well as the attitudes and teachers' performance. Similarly, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between workplace stress and teachers' performance was not rejected. The finding implied that the employee's source of stress had to be recognized since it affected their level of performance. They could manage their stress and its effect yet, were unable to control the different sources of stress. Hence, their performance was inevitable depending on their risks and level of sources of stress around them. Thus it provided unexpected workplace stress due to their teaching performance, workloads and even problems with the learners which were beyond their skills and knowledge. Thus, an action plan as the output of the study was presented.

Keywords: *level of stress, burnout, teachers performance, descriptive-correlational*

Introduction

Teaching is the noblest profession because it is the source of all professionals in the world. Without teachers, there will be no knowledge that was imparted and transferred. In order to continuously improve the educational system, healthy teachers are needed to maintain a happy environment in the classroom. Thus, managing stress in the workplace is one of the important situations that a teacher should aim in order to succeed.

Effective stress management helps you break the hold stress has on your life, so you can be happier, healthier, and more productive. The ultimate goal is a balanced life, with time for work, relationships, relaxation, and fun—and the resilience to hold up under pressure and meet challenges head on. How do you know if your teacher is stressed? Common symptoms include irritability, mood swings and exhaustion, which may escalate into depression, anxiety and lower quality of life. These symptoms have been identified by teachers reporting high stress. Sixty percent of teachers say they experience job-related stress frequently or always, according to a nationally representative survey by the EdWeek Research Center conducted in July. Just 9 percent say they never or rarely do. A primary source of stress and burnout in the classroom is low self-efficacy, or a teacher's lack of belief in them to achieve their goals. Behavioral issues in class can also lead to teacher burnout over time.

Work related stress in teaching had been a topic that received increasing attention to every school administration and the teachers. Teachers mostly devoted their time at school meeting the huge volume of work. This was oftentimes the common complaint of the teachers since they had no time for leisure activities and family. As experienced by the researcher himself, teacher even forgot to care about oneself that sometimes made them sick physically and suffer emotionally due to stressful works in school. Their health was even taken for granted; they developed forgetfulness that having a good health was their prior instrument for them to persist rendering their quality service.

In other words, the success of an educational program of the school depended largely upon the effective way of the teacher's performance. Teachers were the medium and instrument who provide knowledge, instruction, direction and meaning to all the activities of the school. Besides, among all of the different jobs, learning and growing opportunities available in a teaching profession might lead to unhealthy levels of workplace stress which hinder teacher's ways to socialize, perform what is expected, and achieve organizational goals. Recognizing the sources of stress, its effects, and symptoms was important in preventing it from becoming unmanageable or debilitating in work.

Hence, the researcher created a reflective interest related to occupational stress with teachers' productivity and attitude. The researcher believes that result of this study could give ideas to administrators to ensure an effective management in creating healthy and effective organization. Furthermore, the researcher is capacitated to conduct this research since she also experienced the same. Being a teacher handling elementary graders, she somehow encountered stressful works, and in dealing with the learners.

Thus, researcher would like also to create an avenue to evaluate other's experiences as hers, and what could be the particular prevention. Also, the researcher would like to know the effect of this workplace stress to the teaching performance of the respondents. The researcher had a personal deep inclination to study this topic for the reason that she wanted to assess the workplace stress in the teaching profession, delineate teachers' attitude in their work place, and improve their teaching performance to attain continuous quality improvement of education in the city.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine and assess the workplace stress and attitude in the teaching profession and its relationship to the teaching performance of the teachers in public elementary schools in Pantao Ragat District in the school year 2022-2023. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age,
 - 1.2. sex,
 - 1.3. marital status,
 - 1.4. length of service,
 - 1.5. monthly salary,
 - 1.6. plantilla/position, and
 - 1.7. level of education?
2. What is the level of respondents' workplace stress in terms of:
 - 2.1. academic workload,
 - 2.2. environmental, and
 - 2.3. emotional?
3. What is the level of attitudes of teachers towards work in terms of:
 - 3.1. ethical climate fit,
 - 3.2. organizational commitment,
 - 3.3. job satisfaction,
 - 3.4. self-efficacy, and
 - 3.5. Locus of control?
4. What is the level of the teachers' performance in SY 2022-2023 based on Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF)?
5. Is there a significant difference between the profile of the respondents and workplace stress?
6. Is there a significant relationship between workplace stress in the teaching profession and the level of the attitude of teachers towards their work?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the attitude of the teachers toward their work and the teacher's performance?
8. Is there a significant relationship between workplace stress in teaching profession and the teacher's performance?
9. What action plan can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. The study is descriptive in nature since it opted to investigate the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, marital status, length of service, monthly salary, designation/position, and employment. Also, it included workplace stress in relation to academic, environmental, and emotional; respondents' attitudes towards the organization such as ethical climate fit, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, locus of control, and the teacher's performance as well.

It also utilized the correlation design since it investigated the relationship between the profile of the respondents and workplace stress in teaching profession. Further, it determined the relationship between workplace stress in teaching profession and the attitude of teachers towards the organization; the relationship between the attitude of the teachers towards the organization and the teacher's performance. Lastly, was the relationship between workplace stress in teaching profession and the teacher's performance.

Respondents

Table 1. *The Respondents of the Study*

<i>School Respondents</i>	<i>Total Number of Teachers</i>
Banday Elementary School	12
Cabasagan Elementary School	14
Culubun Primary School	6
Dimayon Elementary School	14
Lomidong Elementary School	14
Pantao Marug Primary School	6
Pantao Ragat Central School	20
Total	86

Respondents were limited to seven (7) public elementary schools within Pantao Ragat District of Division of Lanao del Norte. Thus,

the total of the respondents was eighty-six (86) as included in the study. Only those actual teaching teachers who were itemized were considered as the respondents of the study. They were considered handling subjects actually during the school year 2021 – 2022. They were chosen purposively to answer the needed data for the study.

Instruments

The survey questionnaire was the main instrument used in gathering the needed data. This study adapted and used standardized questionnaires by Domino et al. (2014); yet was modified in accordance with the scope of the study and the nature of the situation. This instrument was conducted to seven public elementary schools in District. To facilitate the analysis of the instrument, it used to analyze data, effects, and interventions. The instrument used the Likert scale of 1 to 4 where strongly agree scored “4” and strongly disagree scored “1”. However, “4” and “2” along with “1” were combined as agree and disagree respectively to facilitate data analysis. Using the tool obtained, Cronbach’s alpha of .70 was considered good for this type of research. Further, this instrumentation adopted was refined and revised with pilot testing. All measurements were made using Likert – type items. Cronbach’s alpha method was used as the measure of internal reliability. All scales demonstrated adequate reliability of 0.70.

The following scoring procedures were used to measure the mentioned variables.

Scoring Procedure for Workplace Stress

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Interval</i>	<i>Description</i>
1	4.10-5.00	Strongly Agree
2	3.20-4.09	Agree
3	2.30-3.19	Disagree
4	1.00-2.79	Strongly Agree

Scoring Procedure for Attitude of Teachers

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Interval</i>	<i>Description</i>
1	4.10-5.00	I love to do
2	3.20-4.09	I like to do
3	2.30-3.19	I think I like to do
4	1.00-2.29	I Never do

Procedure

After securing all necessary permits to conduct the study from the Office of the Division Superintendent of Lanao del Norte down to the elementary school heads, the researcher approached the participating elementary school teachers from district that a study would be performed in their respective schools taken as the respondents. In addition, the result of the evaluation of the respondents was obtained. A list of schedules was distributed to ensure that the respondents attended the data gathering.

All the communications were signed and approved by the concerned personalities including the administrative personnel of St. Peter’s College. During the distribution of the questionnaire to the respondents, the researcher further explained the importance and mechanics on how to answer some parts of it. The respondents answered the questions on the teaching performance based their viewed on how workplace stress affected their teaching performance. Confidentiality of their answers was also assured by the researcher.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in computing and evaluating the data gathered.

For problem 1, Frequency and Percentage were used to describe the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, marital status, length of service, monthly salary, plantilla/position, and level of education.

For problems 2, 3, and 4: Weighted Mean was used to determine the level of respondents’ workplace stress in terms of academic workload, environmental and emotional, the level of attitudes of teachers towards work in terms of ethical climate fit, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy and locus of control and the level of teachers performance in SY 2022-2023 based on Individual Performance Commitment Review and Form (IPCRF).

For problems 5, One-way ANOVA test was used to determine the significant difference between the profile of the respondents and workplace stress

For problem 6, Pearson correlation analysis was used to determine the significant relationship between the workplace stress in teaching profession and the level of attitude of teachers towards their work.

For problems 7 and 8, chi-square test was used to determine the significant relationship between the attitude of the teachers towards their work and the teacher’s performance and the significant relationship between workplace stress in teaching profession and the teacher’s performance.

Results and Discussion

This section focused on presenting the gathered data in a meaningful way to facilitate the discussion, presenting findings, and analysis derived from the survey questionnaire of the respondents. The findings and analysis had incorporated general and cross-tabulation analysis that included demographics, enabling environment, awareness, and motivation.

Problem 1: What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, marital status, length of service, monthly salary, plantilla/position, and level of education?

Table 2. *Age of the Respondents*

<i>Age (in years)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
40-above	29	33.7
31-40	40	46.5
21-30	17	19.8
below-20	0	0.0
Total	86	100.0

Table 2 presents the age profile of the respondents. Result showed that 40 or 46.5% of the total respondents belonged to 31-40 years of age, 29 or 33.7% of them belonged to at least 40 years of age and 17 or 19.8% of them were having 21-30 years of age. The result showed that most of the respondents were aged between 31 – 40 years of age which could be said that they were matured enough approaching the adulthood stage.

The results suggested that respondents at their age were pioneers in exploring more of their profession's sector. They required additional experience to comprehend their line of work as represented by several difficult jobs. The responses also needed to be adaptable for their age group and be able to tolerate stress of any intensity. They might experience pressure and uncertainty related to the work that often affects them. The respondents required to be exposed to various stressors in order to develop their resilience in dealing with various obstacles and tasks despite their personal and workplace stress.

This study was supported by the American Medical Association (2018), which stated that young adults were better able to solve problems, think about their future, appreciate the opinions of others, and understand the long-term effects of their decisions. However, they tended to use these skills inconsistently; as a result, they sometimes did things without thinking first. Many successfully did their work effectively when they could understand the people surrounding them. AMS also said that adulthood was more self-assured and better able to resist pressure in works and family matters. They spent less time than they used to with their families. They were excited and at the same time overwhelmed by the possibilities for their future.

Table 3. *Sex of the Respondents*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	0	0.0
Female	86	100.0
Total	86	100.0

Table 3 presents the sex profile of the respondents. Results described that majority (100%) of the respondents were females, 0% for males. The results showed that all respondents were females which signified that the teaching profession was dominated by women.

The results of the study suggested that since women were more chatty, conversational, self-assured, and passionate about pupils, they performed the profession of teaching more frequently than men. The research revealed that female teachers made up the majority of the elementary school teaching staff and were diligent and committed to their work despite the demands of their home and family obligations, which sometimes lead to stress.

It was reinforced by Gonzales (2018), who stated that the dominance of women in Philippine Education was an accomplished phenomenon. The findings implied that most women were believed to be compassionate and affectionately dedicated in their careers. They exerted selfless efforts to achieve the goals of the school where they were connected. One of the respectable characteristics of women was their ability to sympathize with others and the potential to establish a harmonious relationship with people. Thus, females were more capable of handling different stressful problems encountered in the teaching work since they were hypothesized to be more relational and expressive.

Table 4. *Marital Status of the Respondents*

<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Single	0	0.0
Married	86	100.0
Widow/Separated	0	0.0
Total	86	100.0

Table 4 presents the marital status profile of the respondents. Results revealed that all (100%) of the respondents were married. The results showed all were married which means other responsibilities might stress them aside from their teaching works and

responsibilities.

This implied that married teachers might have rich experiences both in families and in handling students since it reflected their mother's role and care in dealing with their children and students. They might probably expect to know how to handle children to facilitate their learning. However, the fact could not be denied that they might also experience stressful situations in facing their family roles, teaching work, student's behavior, relationship with colleagues, and in being a subordinate. Besides, married teachers were faced with different responsibilities and thus, could cope with any situation that might have in their personal and teaching experiences. Timbang (2018), said that married people could be more mature, responsible, and financially stable. With these, they became better at acting as advisers or consultants in some conflicts that might arise in an organization.

Table 5. Length of Service of the Respondents

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
16-above	27	31.2
11-15	22	25.6
6-10	26	29.2
1-5	12	14.0
Total	86	100.0

Table 5 presents the teaching experience profile of the respondents. Result described that nearly half 27 or (31.2%) of the respondents had experience in teaching for 16 and more years, 26 or (29.2%) of them had been in service between 6 – 10 years, 22 or (25.6%) were above 11 to 15 years, and few 12 or (14.0%) were 1 – 5 years in service. The findings showed that it was congruent with the result in their age range; and thus, signified that the respondents were not novices and rookies which somehow stressed them to overcome the hit of hard work.

With this number of years in teaching experience, it was expected that respondents were more aggressive and competitive in teaching for they were still in service for a number of years. Furthermore, length of service had been, since time immemorial, proven to be very important in teaching. Amateur teachers who were eager to teach. Wide experience in teaching was vital to aware oneself from knowing their student's multiple intelligence and diversity to understand their weaknesses and strengths. The finding implied that respondents might have a narrow or limited understanding and experience on matters concerning their students and work that led them to meet stressful challenges and problems.

Indeed, stress as a situation in which an individual was forced to act, and could bear the received mental tension. In other words, stress meant the readjustment of an individual with new situations and conditions. Whenever a change occurred in life, the individual was confronted with stress. Likewise, if the teachers took care of these factors, their performance could be enhanced to the optimum level (Rao & Kumar, 2018). Teachers' entrance and exit examination scores, years of experience, advanced degrees, and teaching credentials were either not related to student achievement or ratings of teacher effectiveness.

Table 6. Monthly Salary Range of the Respondents

<i>Monthly Salary Range</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
40,001-above	0	0.0
30,001-40,000	5	5.8
20,001-30,000	81	94.2
15,001-20,000	0	0.0
10,001-15,000	0	0.0
below-10,000	0	0.0
Total	86	100.0

Table 6 presents the monthly salary profile of the respondents. Results described that the majority (94.2%) of the respondents' earned 20,001-30,000 monthly and five of them (5.8%) earned 30,001-40,000. The finding showed that the majority of the respondents earned financially which could be considered enough for survival. The findings implied that respondent's monthly income could be considered enough for survival especially since the majority of them were married and had other personal responsibilities aside from work. This kind of financial set-up might provide them with stressful encounters with other priorities in life and thus, might also affect their job performance.

Connectively, Leigh, and Mead (2018) brought about the fact that the quality of teaching had come down gradually the world over; and demonstrated that the skills of teachers had come down due to outdated preparation on the part of the teacher and stagnant compensation schemes by the management of the educational institution. This condition in recent years for the teacher led to (1) very few growth opportunities (2) inadequate compensation structure.

Table 7 presents the designation profile of the respondents. Result described that the greater majority involved 53 or (61.6%) of the respondents were Teacher I in designation, 20 or (20.3%) of them were Teacher III, 10 or (11.6%) were Teacher II, and three (3) of them or (3.5%) were Master Teachers I. The findings showed that respondents were still adjusting to the demand of teaching work. The findings of the study were congruent with the respondent's years of experience since most of the teachers were the teacher I who lack more professional growth and experience as reflected for being not promoted in rank.

Table 7. Designation or Position of the Respondents

Designation or Position	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Teacher I	53	61.6
Teacher II	10	11.6
Teacher III	20	23.3
Master teacher I	3	3.5
Total	86	100.0

This implied that many of the respondents had not yet been promoted to a higher position. This was also due to the reason that most of the teachers had served for a short period based on their years in service. Teachers should enroll professionally in master's degrees or other related fields to be more appended and expert in their job performance. They must be equipped with various appropriate strategies applicable in their field of specialization. They should manage the stress which they encountered on their day-to-day life basis. Likewise, they had to continually perform better in teaching with satisfying compensation to prevent stress financially and psychologically. The thought to be promoted might also stress the respondents.

It is in line with human motivation according to Rosenberg (2018) who viewed it as dynamic because what motivated one person today might not motivate him/her at all or to the same degree the next day. Motivation as being biologically driven to satisfy personal physiological needs (e.g., Maslow's conception), biological needs played a role in motivation, much of what drives motivation to do or not do something came from the need to feel effective and demonstrate mastery of the environment. The motivation was something that initiates, sustains, and directs thinking and behavior. It caused one to act and perform his job better like teaching well.

Table 8. Level of Education of the Respondents

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage (%)
College Graduate	41	47.7
With Master's unit earned	25	29.1
Full-fledge Master degree holder	20	23.3
With units in PhD	0	0.0
PhD graduate	0	0.0
Total	86	100.0

Table 8 presents the educational level of the respondents. Descriptive result showed that 47% of the respondents were Bachelor's degree holders, 29% earned units in their masters degree, and 23% of them responded that they had Master degrees. Despite dominating middle age, only few had finished their master's degree which signified a higher rate of completion in undergraduate. A study of Santos (2019) revealed that most of the DepEd teachers did not prioritize entering master's degree or may not have enough time in entering to a higher level due to their hectic schedule. Teachers who desired to grow in their profession can acknowledge that additional advance degree would extremely beneficial. Master's degree holders entering the workplace had a substantial advantage over those who only hold a bachelor's degree. Many organizations not only recognized the benefits of a master's degree but even preferred their employees to have one (Shulsinger, 2018).

Problem 2: What is the level of respondents' workplace stress in terms of academic workload, environmental, and emotional?

Table 9. Level of Respondents' Workplace Stress in Terms of Academic Workload

Indicators	Mean ± SD	Description
1. Low/Inadequate salary	1.59±0.68	Agree
2. Too many papers works to do	1.67±0.66	Agree
3. Work overload	1.60±0.71	Agree
4. Inadequate resources	1.62±0.65	Agree
5. Uncertainty about promotion	1.99±0.73	Agree
6. Work/family conflict	2.15±0.85	Agree
7. Mismatch of subjects and field of specialization	2.69±1.01	Disagree
8. Excessive supervision and criticism	2.34±0.64	Agree
9. Rigid and authoritative system	2.50±0.61	Disagree
10. Competition with co-workers	2.83±0.65	Disagree
Total Measure	2.10±0.51	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Agree; 1.50-2.49, Agree; 2.50-3.49, Disagree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Disagree

Table 9 presents the level of respondents' workplace stress in terms of academic workload. Result depicted that the respondents agreed that academic workload contributed to their stress in the workplace. Specifically, the teachers agreed that some stress resulted to their excessive supervision criticism (M=2.34, SD=0.64) but they disagreed that their academic workload stresses were linked to competition with co-workers (M=2.83, SD=0.65), This implied that respondents received proper treatment from their superiors. They might have established a positive relationship with their superiors and colleagues that made them less stressed although somehow there might be a misunderstanding. They might likewise able to handle problems within their personal life that lessen their stress.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents on their stressors of employees got an average score of 2.10 and a variation of 0.51. It meant that respondents were able to manage somehow their sources of stress relating to their work, and other uncertainties. Bruckheim (2018) pointed out that stress could be brought out by both positive and negative things in one's life. People who were stress survivors stay healthy through that worst time. They considered stressful conditions as opportunities for growth. While on the negative side, such situations could include loss of appetite, children who misbehave, money problems and not enough time with loved ones, lack of shared family responsibility, and dozens of other things. Positive stressors might include positive results.

Table 10. *Level of Respondents' Workplace Stress in Terms of Emotional Aspects*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Anxiety/Worry	2.55±0.52	Disagree
2.	Depression	2.63±0.49	Disagree
3.	Anger	2.86±0.51	Disagree
4.	Overworking	2.27±0.77	Agree
5.	Moodiness	2.78±0.56	Disagree
6.	Loneliness	2.95±0.43	Disagree
7.	Lack of confidence	2.59±0.49	Disagree
8.	High blood pressure	2.76±0.46	Disagree
9.	Headache	2.38±0.67	Agree
10.	Body pain due to over fatigue	2.44±0.57	Agree
	Total Measure	2.62±0.37	Disagree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Agree; 1.50-2.49, Agree; 2.50-3.49, Disagree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Disagree

Table 10 presents the level of occupational stress in terms of symptoms of stress. Results depicted that the respondents had high levels of stress symptoms relative to overworking (M=2.27, SD=0.77). The results implied that respondents experienced workplace stress which was manifested in the mentioned symptoms. Being in the teaching profession was not that easy. Teachers experienced a lot of hard times and excessive workloads that hardly made them incapable to manage. Teaching was the noblest profession; yet, one of the stressful work due to various encounters and experiences. Yet, the respondents had a low level of stress symptoms relative to loneliness (M=2.95, SD=0.53). This implied that although respondents showed fewer symptoms of stress, it did not lead to severe effects as mentioned. It might also challenge the respondents to be more confident and stronger in overcoming problems they encountered. It made them more vigorous and persistent to impart their knowledge and expertise. However, if stress were not managed properly and preventively, it might become worst and defective on the personality, behavior, self-concept, and self-esteem of a person.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing their symptoms of stress were quite low with an average score of 2.62 and a variation of 0.37. Relatively, teachers were bombarded with school tasks and other school-related activities which somehow weakened their body, mind, and soul. They tended to experience various negative reactions of the body which they thought to be a minor disease or illness. Those physical reactions might be just a symptom of stress without their knowledge. The teacher must be aware of the different negative physical reactions such as headaches, back pains, fatigue, fear, and anxiety which could be just a symptom of stress.

Elliot (2018) enumerated various symptoms of stress which helped in identifying the extent of stress that a person was experiencing. Moreover, the symptoms of stress-induced illness may suggest disease in any part of the body. Patients often feel multi-symptoms including various combinations of the following: nervousness, sweating, trembling, fatigue, faintness, indigestion, headache, neck pain, and back pain, shortness of breath, and chest pain. These symptoms might reflect real disease. A heart attack was a real, threatening disease, and indigestion might represent a peptic ulcer, a very real source in the stomach. Thus, identifying one's stress also might help a teacher from dying earlier.

Table 11. *Level of Respondents' Workplace Stress in Terms of Environmental*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Working below par	2.78±0.60	Disagree
2.	Conflict with employees	2.87±0.50	Disagree
3.	Seeking employment elsewhere (Moonlighting)	2.67±0.52	Disagree
4.	Unimproved performance	2.87±0.40	Disagree
5.	Lack motivation and easily disruptive	2.80±0.43	Disagree
6.	Lack of satisfaction	2.83±0.47	Disagree
7.	Unable to submit paper woks on time	2.85±0.39	Disagree
8.	Refuse to accept changes	2.86±0.38	Disagree
9.	Low self-esteem and self-concept	2.73±0.47	Disagree
10.	Inefficient and Ineffective	2.84±0.43	Disagree
	Total Measure	2.81±0.35	Disagree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Agree; 1.50-2.49, Agree; 2.50-3.49, Disagree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Disagree

Table 11 presents the level of workplace stress in terms of its effects. Results depicted that the respondents had a low level of stress effects relative to all the indicators such as conflict with employees (M=2.87, SD=0.50) and unimproved performance (M=2.87, SD=0.40).

The findings above showed that the effects of stress on the respondents did not reflect timely with their workplace stress. It meant that respondents might be able to handle stress since it showed their disagreement on its effects. Although respondents were quite stressed. They performed their work with confidence and motivation. They tended to attain positive regard in recognizing their responsibilities as teachers and work with high self-regard effectively and efficiently. They managed their work and responsibilities even though they felt the symptoms of stress. They were able to look at the positive side of life, improve their performance, and able to maintain a positive self-image and identity.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showed the effects of stress awareness was quite low with an average score of 2.81 and variation of 0.35. It meant that the respondents were quite capable of overcoming their stress and faced challenges with optimism.

According to Hart (2019), stress was the wear and tear of the body's experience as a person subject to his continually changing environment. It had physical and emotional effects on him and could create positive or negative feelings. As a positive influence, stress could help compel him into action. It could result in new awareness and exciting new perspectives. As a negative influence, it could result in a feeling of distrust, anger, rejection, and depression, which in turn led to health problems, with the death of a loved one, the birth of a child, a job promotion, or a new relationship. This meant that respondents experienced stress as they adjusted to their lives, work, and problems.

Table 12. Consolidated Findings of the Level of Respondents' Workplace Stress

Components	Mean \pm SD	Description
Academic Workload	2.10 \pm 0.51	Agree
Emotional Aspects	2.62 \pm 0.37	Disagree
Environmental	2.81 \pm 0.35	Disagree
Total Measure	2.51 \pm 0.33	Disagree

Note: .00-1.49, Strongly Agree; 1.50-2.49, Agree; 2.50-3.49, Disagree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Disagree

Table 12 presents the consolidated findings of the level of workplace stress. Results depicted that the respondents had a high level of workplace stress relative to the academic workload ($M=2.10$, $SD=0.51$). On the other hand, the respondents had a low level of workplace stress relative to the environmental ($M=2.81$, $SD=0.35$). The findings implied that workplace stress affected respondent's performance but, it was based on their responses either positively or negatively. Respondents experienced and felt symptoms of stress but neglected to perceive its effects since they were able to cope up with it.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing their level of workplace stress were quite low with an average score of 2.51 and a variation of 0.33. The general findings garnered that respondents experienced workplace stress in their teaching profession that might also affect their job performance. The work of a teacher is demanding. Thus, it provided unexpected workplace stress due to their teaching performance, workloads, and even problems with the learners which were beyond their skills and knowledge.

According to Muhammad (2019), workplace stress is stress related to one's job. It often stemmed from unexpected responsibilities and pressures that did not align with a person's knowledge, skills, or expectations. It inhibited one's ability to cope. It could lead to one's physical or mental state in response to a workplace that posed a challenge to that employee. Workplace stress should be both at organizational and individual levels.

Problem 3: What is the level of the attitude of teachers towards their work in terms of ethical climate fit, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, and locus of control?

Table 13. Level of Attitude of Teachers Towards Their Work in Terms of Ethical Climate Fit

Indicators	Mean \pm SD	Description
1. Follow organizational goals, rules, and conditions	3.50 \pm 0.53	I love to do
2. Respect one's own personal and moral beliefs	3.52 \pm 0.53	I love to do
3. Decide freely based on right and wrong	3.60 \pm 0.54	I love to do
4. Accept individual differences in the organization	3.60 \pm 0.52	I love to do
5. Act responsibly in the organization	3.62 \pm 0.51	I love to do
Total Measure	3.57 \pm 0.47	Always

Note: 1.00-1.49, I Never Do; 1.50-2.49, I Think I Like to Do; 2.50-3.49, I Like to Do; 3.50-4.00, I Love to Do

Table 13 presents the level of teachers' attitudes in terms of ethical climate fit. Results depicted that the respondents had a very high level of ethical climate fit relative to all the indicators especially on acting responsibly in the organization ($M=3.62$, $SD=0.51$). Thus, the respondents assessed that they had an excellent work attitude on ethical climate fit and values performance in the organization.

The findings implied that the respondents were attuned to professional ethical standards in teaching despite stressful encounters with colleagues, superiors, and students as well. They divulged the vitality of moral development and social harmony in maintaining a positive environment. They respected social diversity, multiculturalism, and individual differences among each other which were pivotal in an organization, particularly in making a decision, task performance, and in attaining the organizational goals and objectives. The teacher's attitude was ideally contemplated and manifested positively.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing their ethical climate fit were quite very high with an average score of 3.57 and a variation of 0.47. The general findings garnered that respondents' attitude was aligned with the basic principles in the code of ethics for teachers. It generally involved establishing a harmonious relationship with others, maintaining moral and social development, and uplifting positive attitudes with the students. The most respected profession in the world was a teacher. He is a model and is consciously imitated.

According to Panda and Mohanty, (2018) the teacher is the pivot of any education system. Teachers are the strength of a nation. They develop performance style characteristics and attitudes to their ways of relating to the world, perceptually as well as cognitively. A person is, therefore, likely to act in a way that maximizes the use of his aptitudes. Similarly, the teacher's positive attitude towards teaching and higher aspiration level determined his positive perception of the environment. Another characteristic of quality/successful teachers is good interpersonal skills.

Table 14. *Level of Attitude of Teachers Towards their Work in Terms of Organizational Commitment*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Ensures effective and efficient performance of duties and responsibilities	3.59±0.52	I love to do
2.	Accept and comply with organizational values and goals	3.62±0.51	I love to do
3.	Do tasks effectively and efficiently	3.60±0.52	I love to do
4.	Instill time management to participate in and perform school activities	3.59±0.52	I love to do
5.	Work collaboratively with others to achieve the school mission, vision, and objectives	3.42±0.82	I like to do
Total Measure		3.57±0.54	Always

Note: 1.00-1.49, I Never Do; 1.50-2.49, I Think I Like to Do; 2.50-3.49, I Like to Do; 3.50-4.00, I Love to Do

Table 14 presents the level of teachers' attitudes in terms of organizational commitment. Results depicted that the respondents had a very high level of teacher's attitude relative to all the organizational commitment indicators mainly on accepting and complying with organizational values and goals ($M=3.62$, $SD=0.51$). The findings showed that the majority of the respondents executed their duties and responsibilities as teachers perhaps committing themselves to their profession and the entire organization. Although, it might be stressful enough to manage work and duties. Teacher respondents identified themselves with the organization and wanted to continue participating actively in it. It also measured their willingness to remain with the firm in the future despite its stressful effects.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing their organizational commitment were quite very high with an average score of 3.57 and a variation of 0.54. The general findings garnered on respondent's organizational commitment were highly evident as shown in the result. According to Coventry (2019), occupational commitment played an important role in the quality performance of employees. If an individual lacked commitment to work, his performance might not be satisfactory. The behavior of an individual at work greatly matters to this effect. Most individuals worked better if their job was pleasant among friendly companions and in a cheerful setting. Many workers preferred routine work and remaining there to be promoted to a higher, more challenging job. Other values security rather than higher but risky positions. They also wanted to feel important or least acceptable to everybody in the organization.

Table 15. *Level of Attitude of Teachers Towards Their Work in Terms of Job Satisfaction*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Enjoys work with pleasure and excitement	3.00±0.69	I like to do
2.	Strengthen relationships with students and colleagues better	3.38±0.80	I like to do
3.	Attain contentment with the nature and condition of the work	3.48±0.61	I like to do
4.	Love doing work without complaint and remorse	3.30±0.80	I like to do
5.	Embrace gratification of work despite the minimum salary received	3.28±0.81	I like to do
Total Measure		3.29±0.67	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49, I Never Do; 1.50-2.49, I Think I Like to Do; 2.50-3.49, I Like to Do; 3.50-4.00, I Love to Do

Table 15 presents the level of teacher's attitudes in terms of job satisfaction. Results depicted that the respondents had a generally high level of teacher's attitude relative to the job satisfaction indicators mainly on attained contentment with the nature and condition of work ($M=3.48$, $SD=0.61$). The findings showed that the majority of the respondents were highly satisfied with their job even though stress was all around them. They were often satisfied with their work and compensation without complaining which meant that respondents' job satisfaction in their teaching profession was manifested.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing their job satisfaction were quite high with an average score of 3.29 and a variation of 0.67. Job satisfaction was rarely achieved. However, the respondents manifested this despite the stress encountered in work, family, friends, and self. Thus, Locke (2019) expounded that job satisfaction was a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences. It simply showed an individual was with his or her job; whether he or she liked the job or not.

Shann (2018) highlighted the importance of teacher job satisfaction for successful educational reform. Thus, reduction in teacher

turnover and reform in education can be facilitated by identifying variables that impact teachers' job satisfaction relationship to characteristics of teachers' backgrounds, teachers' schools, and teachers' compensation. Working conditions with teachers' job satisfaction are important. Teachers showed their interest in moving and achieving organizational goals and their job commitment and satisfaction increased. Teacher job satisfaction is the predictor of teacher retention and a determinant of teacher commitment which contributes to school effectiveness.

Table 16. *Level of Attitude of Teachers Towards Their Work in Terms of Self-Efficacy*

Indicators	Mean \pm SD	Description
1. Finish school papers diligently on time	2.98 \pm 0.70	I like to do
2. Perform work successfully and creatively	3.43 \pm 0.54	I like to do
3. Accepts failure and mistakes constructively to strengthen work enhancement and improvement.	3.33 \pm 0.85	I like to do
4. Execute work confidently and reliably	3.09 \pm 0.75	I like to do
5. Perform works capably despite of problems	3.40 \pm 0.64	I like to do
Total Measure	3.24 \pm 0.61	I like to do

Note: 1.00-1.49, I Never Do; 1.50-2.49, I Think I Like to Do; 2.50-3.49, I Like to Do; 3.50-4.00, I Love to Do

Table 16 shows the level of teachers' attitudes in terms of self-efficacy. Results depicted that the respondents had a generally very high level of teacher's attitude relative to their self-efficacy to perform work successfully and creatively ($M=3.43$, $SD=0.54$). It meant that the respondents particularly those in public schools were clothed with various school activities and works. Teachers were the busiest among them. Aside from teaching, they had also to perform written paper works which also stressed them. Yet, despite these various responsibilities, they tended to manage them and perform them better with flexibility and creativeness.

On the other hand, teacher respondents generally illustrated a high level of teacher's attitude relative to self-efficacy in finishing school papers diligently on time ($M=2.98$, $SD=0.70$). This meant that respondents often committed themselves to their work by performing necessary tasks and responsibilities in school and in the organization, such as submitting school forms on time, regarding strengths and weaknesses to make work successful and collaboratively, and unminding sets of problems and stresses along with the job performance.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing teacher's attitudes were quite high with an average score of 3.24 and a variation of 0.61. The findings above implied that teachers were optimistic and had powerful expectations on their ability to succeed despite the challenging and stressful work environment. They constantly felt confident of success. These types of teachers had a high sense of responsibility in carrying out any task by demonstrating an earnest effort. They represented a personal assessment of their ability to meet the standards of an organization and improve their teaching skills to achieve better performance.

The above findings were supported by Cayci (2019) as he illustrated that self-efficacy was an individual's belief about his or her abilities to produce desired outcomes. Self-efficacy was more closely related to self-concept. It was the positive or negative perception one had about his or her abilities. Self-efficacy generally referred to the trust an individual had towards himself to produce certain tasks or responsibilities properly and effectively. Self-efficacy was an evaluation of the ability to perform a certain behavior in precise circumstances.

Table 17. *Level of Attitude of Teachers Towards Their Work in Terms of Locus of Control*

Indicators	Mean \pm SD	Description
1. Accomplish jobs based on skills, interests, and fortune	3.15 \pm 0.79	I like to do
2. Perform the job passionately to instill values and receive a salary as the sweat of labor	3.51 \pm 0.55	I love to do
3. Expect promotion due to qualifications and experiences	3.29 \pm 0.82	I like to do
4. Perform work with luck to become an outstanding teacher	3.14 \pm 0.81	I like to do
5. Try hard to improve performance at work	3.29 \pm 0.85	I like to do
Total Measure	3.28 \pm 0.70	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49, I Never Do; 1.50-2.49, I Think I Like to Do; 2.50-3.49, I Like to Do; 3.50-4.00, I Love to Do

Table 17 presents the level of teachers' attitudes in terms of locus of control. Results depicted that the respondents had a high level of teacher attitude relative to the locus of control to perform the job passionately to instill values and receive a salary as the sweat of labor is harder ($M=3.51$, $SD=0.55$). This meant that the respondents were trying their best to perform work effectively. They could perform their work following his will and satisfaction.

On the other hand, teacher respondents generally illustrated a high level of teacher's attitude relative to their locus of control in expecting promotion due to qualifications and experiences ($M=2.29$, $SD=0.82$). It implied that the respondents had strongly believed that they had control over the situations and experiences that affected their lives and teaching performance that caused teaching effectiveness and efficiency.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing teacher's attitudes were quite high with an average score of 3.28 and a variation of 0.70. This implied that teacher's beliefs about the success of a student's failures or success, the organization's effectiveness, and teaching strategy had contributed to their positive attitude in teaching. It was deciphering to what degree the teachers felt like they had control over their classroom and their students. Teacher efficacy was strongly related to student achievement. Phares (2018) stated

that locus of control was a generalized expectancy of success that cuts across specific content areas. Personal and general teacher efficacies were both related to teachers' beliefs that they personally, and all teachers generally, could influence children's learning.

Table 18. Consolidated Findings of the Level of Attitude of Teachers Towards Their Work

Components	Mean \pm SD	Description
Ethical climate fit	3.57 \pm 0.47	I love to do
Organizational commitment	3.57 \pm 0.54	I love to do
Job satisfaction	3.29 \pm 0.67	I like to do
Self-efficacy	3.24 \pm 0.61	I like to do
Locus of control	3.28 \pm 0.70	I like to do
Total Measure	3.39 \pm 0.57	Often

Note: 1.00-1.49, I Never Do; 1.50-2.49, I Think I Like to Do; 2.50-3.49, I Like to Do; 3.50-4.00, I Love to Do

Table 18 illustrates the consolidated findings on the level of attitude of teachers. Results depicted that the respondents had a very high level of teacher's attitude relative to ethical climate fit ($M=3.57$, $SD=0.47$), and organizational commitment ($M=3.57$, $SD=0.54$). The findings implied that the respondents showed commitment to the organization ethically, socially, and personally. Their positive attitudes manifested a passionate teacher regardless of their stressful encounters and glitches in life.

On the other hand, teacher respondents generally illustrated a high level of teacher's attitude relative to job satisfaction ($M=3.29$, $SD=0.67$). It implied that the respondents performed their jobs with contentment and a sense of affectivity. They believed that they made changes in the classroom and the organization as a whole. The respondents believed to have control over things could start positive changes and adoption, although, there were stressful circumstances they might face in their teaching profession journey.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing teacher's attitudes were quite high with an average score of 3.39 and a variation of 0.57. It meant that the positive attitude of a teacher could make a difference in the world of education. The most respected profession in the world is a teacher. He is a model and is consciously imitated. According to Panda and Mohanty (2019), the teacher is the pivot of any education system. Teachers were the strength of a nation. They developed performance style characteristics to their ways of relating to the world, perceptually as well as cognitively. Similarly, the teacher's positive attitude towards teaching and higher aspiration level determined his positive perception of the environment. It was universally recognized that teachers' instructional performance played a key role in students' learning and academic achievement.

Problem 4: What is the level of the teachers' performance based on Individual Performance Commitment Review and Form (IPCRF)?

Table 19. Level of the Teachers' Performance

Level of Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very Satisfactory	83	96.5
Outstanding	3	3.5
Total	86	100.0

Table 19 depicts the level of teacher performance. Results depicted that the majority (96.5%) of the respondents' performance results were very satisfactory and 3 or (3.5%) were outstanding. The findings showed that most of the Pantao Ragat public teachers were performing very satisfactorily in their teaching job.

The above findings implied that despite the different workplace stress they encountered that might affect teachers' performance, they could still manage well their time and exert efforts in doing their duties and responsibilities professionally and socially even how stressful it could be. This further implied that teacher respondents were performing effectively and efficiently in their related job tasks. Teachers performed exceedingly from what was expected from them. Their goals, objectives, and other targets in teaching were achieved and established standard performance. They portrayed positive attitudes despite all the hurdles and workplace stress. Teachers could separate their concerns from their jobs which helped them become committed to working.

According to Muzamil and Shawkat (2018), job performance assessed whether a person performed well. Performance was an important criterion for organizational outcomes and success. Likewise, Rao and Kumar (2019) added that the performance of teachers mainly depended on the teachers' characteristics such as knowledge base, sense of responsibility, and inquisitiveness. The students' characteristics such as the opportunity to learn, and academic work; the teaching factors such as lesson structure, and communication; the learning aspects such as involvement and success; and the classroom were considered. If the teachers took care of these factors, their performance could be enhanced to the optimum level.

Problem 5: Is there a significant difference between the profile of the respondents and workplace stress?

Table 20 presents the difference on the level of workplace stress when grouped to their age using the One-way ANOVA test. Result showed that the level of workplace stress of the respondents was comparable across their age ($F=0.502$, $p=0.607$). Further, the teachers have comparable level of stress relative to academic workload, emotional aspects, and environmental aspects across their age differences. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference on the level of workplace stress when grouped to their age was not

rejected.

Table 20. Difference1 on the Level of Workplace Stress When Grouped to Their Age

Workplace Stress	Age Group			F-value (p-value)	Remarks
	40-above (n=29)	31-40 (n=40)	21-30 (n=17)		
Academic	2.05±0.48	2.08±0.55	2.23±0.46	0.733 (0.484)	Not significant
Emotional	2.51±0.39	2.66±0.35	2.71±0.35	2.124 (0.126)	Not significant
Environmental	2.84±0.29	2.81±0.39	2.76±0.40	0.278 (0.758)	Not significant
Total Measure	2.47±0.31	2.52±0.34	2.57±0.34	0.502 (0.607)	Not significant

Note: 1-Analysis is based on One-way ANOVA not significant (p-value > 0.05)

Table 20 presents the difference on the level of workplace stress when grouped to their age using the One-way ANOVA test. Result showed that the level of workplace stress of the respondents was comparable across their age ($F=0.502$, $p=0.607$). Further, the teachers have comparable level of stress relative to academic workload, emotional aspects, and environmental aspects across their age differences. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference on the level of workplace stress when grouped to their age was not rejected.

The findings revealed that respondents at their age were trailblazers in discovering more of the industry related to their careers. They needed more experience to understand their field of work, which was reflected by a number of challenging jobs. Additionally, the responses are required to be age-appropriate and able to withstand stress of any degree. They could feel pressure and uncertainty because of the work that frequently has an impact on them. To build their resilience in dealing with challenges and duties despite their personal and professional stress, the responders needed to be exposed to a variety of stressors.

As population aging becomes a global trend, exhaustion and prolonged working age have been issues for older workers. Active aging is expected not only to prolong working years but also to increase age integration and reduce intergenerational conflicts. The willingness to work and the effects of working ability on health and well-being could be the core issues for an aging society (Leigh, 2018). However, whether the negative impacts of exhaustion on well-being can be reduced or avoided via individuals' working methods or attitudes, or by systemic and policy changes for both younger and older workers had been little explored (Bradley, 2018).

Table 21. Difference1 on the Level of Workplace Stress When Grouped to Their Length of Service

Workplace Stress	Length of Service Group				F-value (p-value)	Remarks
	≥ 16 (n=26)	11-15 (n=22)	6-10 (n=26)	1-5 (n=12)		
Academic	2.03±0.57	2.04±0.54	2.15±0.42	2.23±0.50	0.640 (0.591)	Not significant
Emotional	2.53±0.38	2.71±0.39	2.63±0.32	2.63±0.40	1.038 (0.380)	Not significant
Environmental	2.86±0.22	2.85±0.38	2.74±0.44	2.79±0.35	0.612 (0.609)	Not significant
Total Measure	2.47±0.34	2.53±0.36	2.51±0.28	2.55±0.38	0.205 (0.893)	Not significant

Note: 1-Analysis is based on One-way ANOVA not significant (p-value > 0.05)

Table 21 presents the difference on the level of workplace stress when grouped to their length of service using the One-way ANOVA test. Result disclosed that the level of workplace stress of the respondents was comparable across their length of service ($F=0.205$, $p=0.893$). Moreover, the teachers have comparable level of stress relative to academic workload, emotional aspects and environmental aspects across their length of service. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference on the level of workplace stress when grouped to their length of service was not rejected.

It was anticipated that responders with this amount of teaching experience would be more aggressive and competitive in their teaching because they had remained in the profession for a considerable amount of time. Furthermore, it has long been known that duration of service is crucial in the teaching profession. amateur instructors ready to share their knowledge. It was essential to have extensive teaching experience in order to be aware of your students' diverse intellect and to comprehend their strengths and flaws. The results suggested that respondents may have had a limited or narrow grasp of issues relating to their pupils and jobs, which caused them to encounter difficult obstacles and issues.

Working organizational factors, including labor policies, working conditions, interpersonal support, and even workplace leadership and management, affect the workload, stress, and exhaustion levels of workers. Being in the workplace for a long period signified lower level of job control and decreased social support at work which are related to a higher risk of being passive. Physical workload, high task resources, and good leadership are related to better workability disregarding the so-called of length of service (Pisanti et al., 2018).

Table 22 presents the difference on the level of workplace stress when grouped to their monthly salary range using the Independent t-test analysis. Result revealed that the level of workplace stress of the respondents was comparable across their monthly salary range ($t=0.954$, $p=0.343$). In addition, the teachers have comparable level of stress relative to academic workload, emotional aspects and environmental aspects across their monthly salary differences. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference on the level of workplace stress when grouped to their monthly salary range was not rejected.

The results suggested that respondents' monthly salary may be regarded as sufficient for survival, particularly given that the majority of them were married and had other obligations outside of work. Their unpleasant interactions with other life goals may result from

this type of financial arrangement, which may also have an impact on how well they perform at work.

Table 22. *Difference2 on the Level of Workplace Stress When Grouped to Their Monthly Salary Range*

Workplace Stress	Monthly Salary Range Group		t-value (p-value)	Remarks
	30001-40000 (n=5)	20001-30000 (n=81)		
Academic	2.44±0.21	2.08±0.52	1.563 (0.122)	Not significant
Emotional	2.58±0.40	2.62±0.37	-0.254 (0.800)	Not significant
Environmental	2.92±0.27	2.80±0.36	0.710 (0.480)	Not significant
Total Measure	2.65±0.17	2.50±0.34	0.954 (0.343)	Not significant

Note: 2-Analysis is based on Independent T-test not significant (p-value > 0.05)

As a result of outdated preparation on the part of the teachers and stagnant compensation plans by the management of the educational institution, Leigh and Mead (2018) connected the fact that the quality of teaching had gradually declined throughout the world and showed how this had affected the skills of teachers. Due to these circumstances, teachers have had (1) little possibilities for professional development and (2) an unsatisfactory remuneration system in recent years.

Table 23. *Difference1 on the Level of Workplace Stress When Grouped to Their*

Workplace Stress	Designation Group			F-value (p-value)	Remarks
	Teacher I (n=53)	Teacher II (n=10)	Teacher III/MT I (n=23)		
Academic	2.03±0.51	2.09±0.38	2.27±0.54	1.800 (0.172)	Not significant
Emotional	2.59±0.38	2.62±0.36	2.69±0.36	0.520 (0.597)	Not significant
Environmental	2.80±0.33	2.67±0.48	2.90±0.34	1.489 (0.231)	Not significant
Total Measure	2.47±0.34	2.46±0.31	2.62±0.31	1.652 (0.198)	Not significant

Note: 1-Analysis is based on One-way ANOVA not significant (p-value > 0.05)

Table 23 presents the difference on the level of workplace stress when grouped to their designation using the One-way ANOVA test. Result displayed that the level of workplace stress of the respondents was comparable across their designation (F=1.652, p=0.198). Further, the teachers have comparable levels of workplace stress relative to academic workload, emotional aspects and environmental aspects across their designation. High-ranking teachers and lower-ranking teachers have the same amount of workplace stress. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the level of workplace stress when grouped to their designation was not rejected.

Since the majority of the instructors were teachers I, who lack greater professional development and experience as evidenced by not being promoted in rank, the study's findings were consistent with the respondent's years of experience.

This suggested that a large portion of the respondents had not yet received a promotion to a more senior post. This was also a result of the fact that, according to their years of service, the majority of the teachers had only been employed for a little time. To be more qualified and proficient in their work, teachers should pursue master's degrees or other degrees in related subjects (Llego, 2018).

On the other hand, according to Santos (2018), an individual's ability to maintain a balance between work and life is affected by factors relating to an individual's workplace status position or designation, and working conditions, including the flexibility and quantity of hours worked, sick and holiday leave provisions, and availability of support structures within the workplace. This status designation is a crucial factor for teacher in their work proficiency.

Table 24. *Difference1 on the Level of Workplace Stress When Grouped to Their Level of Education*

Workplace Stress	Level of Education Group			F-value (p-value)	Remarks
	College Graduate (n=41)	With Master Unit (n=25)	Master (n=20)		
Academic	2.04±0.45	2.13±0.67	2.18±0.38	0.554 (0.577)	Notsignificant
Emotional	2.59±0.37	2.54±0.42	2.79±0.26	2.962 (0.057)	Notsignificant
Environmental	2.82ab±0.30	2.68a±0.40	2.95b±0.35	3.585* (0.032)	Significant
Total Measure	2.48±0.29	2.45±0.43	2.64±0.23	2.098 (0.129)	Not significant

Note: 1-Analysis is based on One-way ANOVA *-significant at 0.05 level not significant (p-value > 0.05) ab-based on Duncan test

Table 24 presents the difference on the level of workplace stress when grouped to their level of education using the One-way ANOVA test. Result showed that the level of workplace stress of the respondents was comparable across their level of education (F=2.098, p=0.129). Further, the teachers have comparable level of workplace stress relative to academic workload, and emotional aspects across their level of education. Master degree holder teachers and teachers with master unit have same amount of academic workload and emotional stress. However, the teachers with master degree (M=2.95) have higher level of environmental stress as compared to those teachers with master unit (M=2.68). Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference on the level of workplace stress when grouped to their level of education was not rejected.

Few people had completed their master's degree despite the majority of them being in middle age, which indicated a greater percentage

of undergraduate completion. According to a Santos (2019) study, the majority of DepEd teachers did not prioritize pursuing a master's degree or may not have had enough time due to their busy schedules. A second advanced degree would be very helpful for teachers who wanted to improve in their careers. When entering the workforce, those with master's degrees had a significant edge over those with only a bachelor's degree. Many businesses not only valued the advantages of a master's degree but also insisted that their staff hold one (Shulsinger, 2018).

Problem 6: Is there a significant relationship between the workplace stress in teaching profession and the level of the attitude of teachers towards their work?

Table 25. Relationship3 Between the Workplace Stress in Teaching Profession and the Level of Attitude of Teachers Towards their Work

Attitude	Workplace Stress			
	Academic	Emotional	Environmental	Total Measure
Ethical climate fit	-0.222* (0.040)	-0.126 (0.248)	-0.238* (0.027)	-0.246* (0.022)
Organizational commitment	-0.340** (0.001)	-0.155 (0.155)	-0.196 (0.070)	-0.302** (0.005)
Job satisfaction	-0.419** (0.000)	-0.154 (0.158)	-0.162 (0.137)	-0.330** (0.002)
Self-efficacy	-0.408** (0.000)	-0.189 (0.081)	-0.163 (0.133)	-0.338** (0.001)
Locus of control	-0.429** (0.000)	-0.261* (0.015)	-0.104 (0.342)	-0.354** (0.001)
Total Measure	-0.393** (0.000)	-0.191 (0.078)	-0.175 (0.107)	-0.335** (0.002)

Note: Values expressed in r-value (p-value) 3-Analysis is based on Pearson Product Moment Correlation *-significant at 0.05 level **-significant at 0.01 level Total measure means average values of the given components of the main variable.

Table 25 presents the relationship between the workplace stress in teaching profession and the level of attitude of teachers towards their work using the Pearson correlation analysis. Result revealed that the workplace stress and the attitude of teachers have negative correlation ($r=-0.335, p=0.002$). In addition, the academic workload stress of the teachers was significantly and negatively correlated to the locus of control ($r=-0.429, p=0.000$). These results implied that the teachers having high levels of academic workload stress could have lowered their locus of control. However, the higher level of emotional and environmental stress manifested by the teachers could not be significantly related to their attitude toward their work since the observed p-values exceeded at the 0.05 level. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the workplace stress in teaching profession and the level of attitude of teachers towards their work was rejected.

The findings implied that when teachers were experiencing workplace stress, they performed less more than what was expected from them. They might show unusual reactions and negative attitudes towards the organization when they were under stress. Although they had some stress intervention management, it did not guarantee that the effect of stress could not be manifested in their job performance and commitment. The effects of stress might also be reflected in teacher's performance, their locus of control in performing their beliefs; and their self-efficacy might be less effective and efficient.

The American Psychiatric Association (2018) claimed that stress was a sense of being overwhelmed, worry, destruction, press, exhaustion, and lethargy. Therefore, stress could influence people in every situation and could result in both physical and psychological health. Thus, their attitude might be affected depending on the process of their reaction towards a certain stressor as it affected their thinking, beliefs, attitudes, and perceptions.

Problem 7: Is there a significant relationship between the attitude of the teachers towards their work and the teacher's performance?

Table 26. Relationship4 Between the Attitude of the Teachers Towards Their Work and the Teacher's Performance

Attitude	Teacher Performance		Remarks
	Chi-square value (df)	P-value	
Ethical climate fit	2.632 (2)	0.268	Not significant
Organizational commitment	2.856 (2)	0.240	Not significant
Job satisfaction	3.715 (2)	0.156	Not significant
Self-efficacy	3.715 (2)	0.156	Not significant
Locus of control	1.724 (2)	0.422	Not significant
Total Measure	3.457 (2)	0.178	Not significant

Note: 4-analysis is based on Chi-square test based on Likelihood Ratio not significant means p-value > 0.05

Table 26 shows the relationship between the attitude of the teachers towards their work and the teacher's performance using the Chi-square test based on Likelihood ratio. Result depicted that the attitude of the teachers relative to ethical climate fit, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy and locus of control were not significantly associated to their teaching performance since

the observed p-values exceeded at the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the attitude of the teachers towards their work and the teacher's performance was not rejected.

The findings above implied that the teacher's attitude was reflected in his work performance. They performed better if they felt contented and satisfied with the nature of work they had and the positive climate they were placed in. If they felt compassionate and efficient, they could be more predictive and well-performing. However, their commitment to the work had nothing to do with their attitude since commitment lies along their duties to be fulfilled to attain organizational goals and objectives. The factors of performance were the extent to which a teacher could accomplish the tasks that made up his or her job. A mentor served as a record of outcomes he produced during a specific job, over a specific time. Teachers' performance served as the amount of effort, initiative and absenteeism, maintenance of standards, and commitment displayed by teachers while performing their teaching tasks.

Employees were over their responsibilities. The necessity of good interpersonal relationships among employees to ensure better job performance in the work field could be understood by this analyzed data. It was also found out that the respondents had taken frequent leaves from a job due to their boredom and lack of interest in their current job (Takase et al, 2019). Hence, the higher the job satisfaction, self-efficacy, locus of control, and climate fit, the higher the employee's performance. The data proclaimed the significance of teachers' attitudes among employees to get the best performance from their part.

Problem 8: Is there a significant relationship between workplace stress in teaching profession and the teacher's performance?

Table 27. Relationship⁴ Between the Workplace Stress and the Teacher's Performance

Workplace Stress	Teacher Performance		Remarks
	Chi-square value (df)	P-value	
Academic	2.856 (2)	0.240	Not significant
Emotional	0.034 (1)	0.854	Not significant
Environmental	0.546 (1)	0.460	Not significant
Total Measure	0.512 (1)	0.474	Not significant

Note: 4-analysis is based on Chi-square test based on Likelihood Ratio not significant means p-value > 0.05

Table 27 shows the relationship between the workplace stress of the teachers and the teacher's performance using the Chi-square test based on Likelihood ratio. Result described that the level of workplace stress of the teachers relative to academic workload, emotional aspect, and environment were not significantly associated to their teaching performance since the observed p-values exceeded at the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the workplace stress and the teacher's performance was not rejected.

The findings implied that the employee's source of stress had to be recognized since it affected their level of performance. It was evident from the findings that they could manage their stress and its effect yet, unable to control the different sources of stress. Hence, their performance was inevitable depending on the risks and level of sources of stress around them.

Moreover, the relationship between work stressors and employee's performance according to Divakar (2019) showed the impact of the performance of the employees from different parts. Work-related stress was still a developing concept but it was a reality. According to Ekzada and Tekeste (2018), the causes of stress at the workplace range from personal problems to work overload, the physical working environment, work situations, and conflicts among colleagues and managers. Many employees struggle with stress, in worst cases leading to uncertainties and severe impairments on health and performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings presented in the preceding section, the following conclusions were drawn.

In the teaching profession, female teachers predominated, and the majority of them were married. It is clear from the results that respondents, who are new to the teaching profession, need a lot of experience to fully understand the demands and surroundings of the job. Since they were instructors, they made an effort to perform better in order to pursue promotions and pay raises. They were the majority at public schools, therefore it may be inferred that respondents had the potential to feel pressured and encountered difficulties getting through paperwork and a backlog of obligations to their personal, professional, and social lives.

The workplace stress of the respondents was quite high. Respondents experienced the symptoms and effects of stress yet learned to manage them in their quiet ways. They also experienced the sources of stress related to the changes in their moods and emotions. Thus, the respondents overcame stress-related work to avoid its effect. Naturally, teaching is the hardest profession since teachers dealt with their environment, colleagues, students, parents, and the entire stakeholders which seemed to be the common stressors. If this may not be pressed with attention, it may lead to psychological, health, physical, social, and emotional sickness in which teachers are not minded.

The findings showed that teachers' attitudes were quite positive, indicating that the respondents are committed to the organization on an ethical, social, and personal level. Despite their challenging experiences and life's hiccups, their positive attitude creates a dedicated teacher. They carried out their duties with satisfaction and affectivity. They thought they could alter the classroom and the company as

a whole. Despite potentially difficult situations, the respondents said they had some control over factors that could lead to positive adoption and change in the teaching profession. Thus, a teacher's optimistic outlook may have an impact on the educational landscape.

With the respondents' performance result to be very satisfactory, it can be concluded that they perform their duties and responsibilities satisfactorily by providing the needs of the students and attaining the organizational goals and objectives. Thus, teacher's performance showed a positive result and satisfying service in meeting the needs of the students and the school particularly the community as well as providing quality products of education.

It can likewise be concluded that teachers can perform better even under stress since they had an organizational commitment to fulfill and perform. Although the effect of stress, its symptoms were evident to the respondent's responses, still they were able to apply intervention management to overcome stress across any level. Also, the teacher's attitude had something to do with their performance so the way they perceive their organization as to their satisfaction, locus of control, and self-efficacy inevitably provided positive performance aligned with what an organization should attain. Thus, it is concluded that teachers can perform better if they can attain mental health awareness related to the effect of workplace stress.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following are formulated for a recommendation.

DepEd officials ought to make school forms for teachers shorter. Teachers should be given credit for the labored efforts and unspecified sacrifices they made in order to produce high-quality education.

To assist and support the teachers in managing stress through seminars, programs, and other coping mechanisms, the administrators must have a thorough understanding of the workplace stress that their teachers encounter. They should also develop and implement programs for stress reduction and sensitivity training that are beneficial to the mental health of teachers. They ought to carry out a learning action cell on stress.

The teachers may be able to determine how job stress affects their ability to teach. To develop a good attitude in the workplace, they should participate in various interventions like individual and group therapy, engage in outdoor activities, and maintain interpersonal relationships with coworkers.

Guidance counselors' awareness of the stress instructors experience at work could increase their expertise in providing counseling services to both teachers and students. They should develop and deliver training programs and stress management workshops, as well as provide defense mechanisms to lessen their obstacles and uncertainties in their jobs, families, and personal lives.

This study could serve as a source of information on other studies relating to stress. Other researchers could use the results of this present study to prove or disprove ideas in their studies as well.

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